

soaked for 24 hrs in the test solutions and planted. 2,4-D (sodium salt) was also tested under similar conditions for comparison. The percentage inhibition is recorded in Table 2.

TABLE 2—HERBICIDAL SCREENING

Compound No.	Average percentage Inhibition					
	Weed <i>A. mexicana</i> concentrations used			Weed <i>C. rotundis</i> concentrations used		
	1000 ppm	100 ppm	10 ppm	1000 ppm	100 ppm	10 ppm
1.	60.1	32.1	24.2	53.4	20.7	13.4
2.	61.5	33.4	25.6	54.7	25.4	18.9
3.	55.1	25.4	16.5	51.3	22.7	16.4
2,4-D (Sodium salt)	100	84.2	66.7	100	82.6	61.5

$$\% \text{ Inhibition} = \frac{G_c - G_t}{G_c} \times 100$$

where, G_c = No. of germinated seeds/tubers in control,

G_t = No. of germinated seeds/tubers in test solution/suspension.

Fungicidal screening :

Antifungal activity was evaluated by agar-plate technique^{1,2} against *A. niger* and *H. oryzae* at 1000, 100 and 10 ppm. The number of replication in each case was three. A commercial fungicide Dithane M-45 was tested under similar conditions for comparison. The percentage inhibition is recorded in Table 3.

TABLE 3—FUNGICIDAL SCREENING

Compound No.	Average percentage inhibition after 96 hrs					
	Organism <i>A. niger</i> concentrations used			Organism <i>H. oryzae</i> concentrations used		
	1000 ppm	100 ppm	10 ppm	1000 ppm	100 ppm	10 ppm
1.	52.5	27.3	18.1	47.5	18.3	9.4
2.	57.5	30.1	21.4	57.6	22.4	13.4
3.	55.7	28.5	20.5	51.7	21.1	11.8
Dithane M-45 (a commercial fungicide)	100	85.4	72.6	96.4	82.9	68.3

$$\% \text{ Inhibition} = \frac{(C - T) \times 100}{C}$$

where, C = Diameter of fungus colony in control plates after 96 hrs,

T = Diameter of fungus colony in treated plates after 96 hrs.

It is evident from the screening data (Tables 2 and 3) that all the screened compounds were toxic to weeds (*A. mexicana* and *C. rotundus*) and fungi (*A. niger* and *H. Oryzae*) in varied degrees. Compound No. 2 in both the cases inhibited 50% growth of both the fungi and weed at 1000 ppm and thus appear to be fairly active.

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Synthesis and Fungitoxicity of Some Bicyclic Compounds

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5-Mono-bromo-3-N-phenyl-rhodanine¹ when condensed with acetoacetic ester in presence of ethanol affords 3-N-phenyl-5-(1'-acetyl-1'-carboethoxy methyl)-rhodanine, which on condensation with phenyl hydrazine yields 3-N-phenyl-5-(1'-phenyl - 3'-methyl - 2'-pyrazolin-5'-ones)-rhodanine. This compound also synthesized by two other methods in which 5-mono-bromo-3-phenyl-rhodanine condensed in ethanol with 1-phenyl-3-methyl-2-pyrazolin-5-one and 4-mono-bromo-1-phenyl-3-methyl-2-pyrazolin-5-one in presence of ethanol with 3-N-phenyl-rhodanine afford the same compound. The product obtained by the three methods were found identical from their m. m. p. and superimposition of ir data. The oxidation of the above compound resulting in the conversion of $\text{>C}-\text{C}<$ to $\text{>C}=\text{C}<$ was accomplished by the treatment of the alkaline solution of 3-phenyl-5-(1'-phenyl - 3'-methyl-2'-pyrazolin-5'-one)-rhodanine with saturated solution of iodine in potassium iodide.

In our previous work²⁻⁵ on heterocyclic five membered compounds, we reported the significant

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fungicidal activity of the *bis* compound of 2-pyrazolin-5-ones against the rice blast pathogen *Pyricularia oryzae* and brown leaf spot pathogen *Helminthosporium oryzae*. Literature also reveals that the 3-N-phenyl substituted rhodanine shows encouraging fungicidal⁶ activity. In view of the marked biological importance associated with this class of compounds the present investigation was extended. *Bis* compounds containing both the pyrazolone nuclei and 3-N-phenyl substituted rhodanine nuclei were synthesized and their fungicidal activity was studied against *P. oryzae* and *H. oryzae*. The 3-N-phenyl-5-(1'-phenyl-3'-methyl-2'-pyrazolin-5-one) rhodanine and their oxidation product has been synthesised as outlined below :

Ten *bis* compounds have been prepared by taking ten different 3-N-phenyl substituted rhodanine and their oxidation products have also been prepared and screened for their antifungal activity against the pathogen *P. oryzae* and *H. oryzae* using the spore germination⁷ test at various concentrations. The fungicidal data only at 1000 ppm is

shown in Tables 1 and 2. Compounds Sl. No. 3, 14, 15, 17 did not exhibit significant fungicidal activity while the remaining compounds showed good activity against *P. oryzae*. Highest activity was exhibited by compounds 2 and 8 which inhibit 98 and 100% at 1000 ppm concentration. Compounds Sl. No. 1, 2, 5, 6, 8, 9, 13, 17, 20 are fungicidally active against *H. oryzae*. The remaining compounds are fungicidally inactive against *H. oryzae*. It was concluded from our observation on fungicidal activity of the prepared compounds that oxidation of the *bis* derivatives resulting in the creation of new linkage $>\text{C}=\text{C}<$ decreases the activity considerably.

Experimental

The m.p. and the analytical values of the compounds prepared are listed in Tables 1 and 2. The ir spectra are given in the experiments.

TABLE 1

$$\begin{array}{c} \text{H} \quad \text{H} \\ | \quad | \\ \text{S}-\text{C}-\text{C}-\text{C}-\text{CH}_3 \\ | \quad | \quad | \\ \text{S}=\text{C} \quad \text{C}=\text{O} \quad \text{O}=\text{C} \\ | \quad | \quad | \\ \text{N} \quad \quad \quad \text{N} \\ | \quad \quad \quad | \\ \text{R}_1 \quad \quad \quad \text{R} \end{array} \quad \text{III (1-10)} \\ \text{R}=\text{C}_6\text{H}_5 \text{ (1-10)}$$

Sl. No.	Nature of R ₁	m.p. °C	% inhibition of germination at 1000 ppm	
			<i>P. oryzae</i>	<i>H. oryzae</i>
1.	Phenyl	315	88	59
2.	<i>o</i> -Chloro phenyl	285	98	68
3.	<i>m</i> -Chloro phenyl	205	57	43
4.	<i>p</i> -Chloro phenyl	265	46	55
5.	<i>o</i> -Anisyl	278	78	50
6.	<i>p</i> -Anisyl	282	49	38
7.	<i>p</i> -Ethoxy phenyl	175	50	48
8.	<i>o</i> -Tolyl	275	100	68
9.	<i>m</i> -Tolyl	280	77	50
10.	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	235	42	29

TABLE 2

$$\begin{array}{c} \text{H} \quad \text{H} \\ | \quad | \\ \text{S}-\text{C}=\text{C}-\text{C}-\text{CH}_3 \\ | \quad | \quad | \\ \text{S}=\text{C} \quad \text{C}=\text{O} \quad \text{O}=\text{C} \\ | \quad | \quad | \\ \text{N} \quad \quad \quad \text{N} \\ | \quad \quad \quad | \\ \text{R}_1 \quad \quad \quad \text{R} \end{array} \quad \text{IV (11-20)} \\ \text{R}=\text{C}_6\text{H}_5 \text{ (11-20)}$$

Sl. No.	Nature of R ₁	m.p. °C	% inhibition of germination at 1000 ppm	
			<i>P. oryzae</i>	<i>H. oryzae</i>
11.	Phenyl	80	67	49
12.	<i>o</i> -Chloro phenyl	98	78	56
13.	<i>m</i> -Chloro phenyl	185	38	23
14.	<i>p</i> -Chloro phenyl	170	36	25
15.	<i>o</i> -Anisyl	156	58	35
16.	<i>p</i> -Anisyl	95	42	59
17.	<i>p</i> -Ethoxy phenyl	267	49	38
18.	<i>o</i> -Tolyl	131	80	48
19.	<i>m</i> -Tolyl	73	65	58
20.	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	61	49	30

All the compounds gave satisfactory C, H, N analysis. The yield varied between 45 to 65%.

Preparation of 3-phenyl-5-(1'-acetyl-1'-carboethoxy methyl) rhodanine (III): 3-Phenyl-5-mono-bromorhodanine (0.01 mole) and acetoacetic ester (0.01 mole) were taken in ethanol and refluxed on a water bath for 8 hrs. Excess ethanol was evaporated, cooled and cold water was added. The brown coloured compound thus obtained was filtered, crystallised from glacial acetic acid, m.p. 121°. Gives colouration with FeCl_3 solution, soluble in 10% aq. alkali and gives positive test for ester group ($\text{C}_{15}\text{NS}_2\text{O}_4\text{H}_{15}$ requires, C, 53.40; H, 4.41; N, 4.12; Found C, 53.02; H, 4.23; N, 3.99%).

Preparation of 3-phenyl-5-(1'-phenyl-3'-methyl-5-one) rhodanine: Method I: 3-Phenyl-5-(1'-acetyl-1'-carboethoxy methyl) rhodanine (0.01 mole) was dissolved in minimum quantity of acetic acid. Phenyl hydrazine (0.01 mole) was added to it and the mixture heated for 1 hr on a water bath, cooled and the resulting mixture filtered and crystallised from acetone. Yield 50%, soluble in 10% aq. alkali and gave colouration with FeCl_3 .

Method II: 5-Mono-bromo-3-phenyl-rhodanine (0.01 mole) and 1-phenyl-3-methyl-2-pyrazolin-5-one (0.01 mole) were taken in 25 ml of ethanol followed by fused sodium acetate and refluxed for 4 hrs on a water bath. Excess ethanol was evaporated and the resulting mixture cooled and ice-cold water was added to it. The gummy product was dissolved in 10% aqueous alkali, filtered and the filtrate was acidified with cold dil. HCl. The white compound thus obtained was filtered and crystallised from acetone, soluble in 10% aq. alkali and gave colouration with FeCl_3 solution.

Method III: 1-Phenyl-3-methyl-2-pyrazolin-4-mono-bromo-5-one (0.01 mole) and 3-phenyl-rhodanine (0.01 mole) were taken in 25 ml of ethanol followed by fused sodium acetate and refluxed for 4 hrs on a water bath. The excess ethanol was evaporated and cooled. Ice-cold water was added to it. The gummy mass obtained was dissolved in 10% aq. alkali and acidified with cold dil. HCl. The white compound thus obtained was crystallised from acetone, soluble in 10% aq. alkali and gave colouration with FeCl_3 solution.

The m.p. of the compounds obtained by the three methods was found to be the same and the ir data superimposable with each other. The ir data show the enolic band at 3012 cm^{-1} and the band at 1597 cm^{-1} (ring $> \text{C}=\text{O}$).

Preparation of the oxidation product of 3-phenyl-5-(1'-phenyl-3'-methyl-2'-pyrazolin-5'-one) rhodanine: 3-Phenyl-5-(1'-phenyl-3'-methyl-2'-pyrazolin-5'-one) (2 g) was dissolved in 10% sodium hydroxide solution (20 ml). A saturated solution of iodine in potassium iodide (25 ml) was added with constant stirring for 1 hr. The light blue compound thus obtained was filtered, washed with 10% solution of sodium thiosulphate, finally with water and purified from acetone. Yield 75%. IR data show the presence of ($> \text{C}=\text{O}$) band at 1620 cm^{-1} , enolic band absent.

Following the above procedure we have synthesised ten bis compounds and their ten oxidation product whose physical and fungicidal data are given in the Table 1 and Table 2 respectively.

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Synthesis and Fungitoxicity of Substituted Pyrazolyl Oxazole

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OXAZOLE have been associated with hypertensive¹, analgesic, antiinflammatory^{2,3}, antibacterial, antiviral⁴, antitubercular⁵, anticonvulsant⁶ and antifungal⁷ activities. In our earlier investigation on heterocyclic fungicides⁸⁻¹¹ it was noted that 5-pyrazolone possess significant fungicidal activity against the rice blast pathogen *Pyricularia oryzae* and the brown leaf spot pathogen *Helminthosporium oryzae*. Significant fungicidal activity exhibited by pyrazolyl-thiazole¹²⁻¹⁵ against the above pathogens encouraged us to synthesise a new heterocyclic compound containing both pyrazolone and oxazole moieties with a view to study and compare its fungitoxicity with the corresponding sulphur analogue. The structure of ten compounds thus prepared have been established from satisfactory analytical values, solubility in aq. NaOH and positive test with ethanolic FeCl_3 . IR spectra (cm^{-1}) of Cpd No 2 showed characteristic absorption bands around 3000 (NH coupled with aromatic C-H vibration), 1650 ($\text{C}=\text{O}$), 1610 (phenyl ring) and at 1535 ($\text{C}=\text{C}$). Absence of enolic hydroxyl absorption indicates that in solid state it remains as carbonyl compound but in solution it exists as a mixture of tautomer. The compounds were screened for their antifungal activity against *Pyricularia oryzae* and *Helminthosporium oryzae* by standard method¹⁴ using spore germination tests

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